

Numerical Study on the Buckling Behavior of Fiber-Metal Laminates (FML) with Defects

Chuanjun Liu*, Peter Linde, Juergen Pleitner
Airbus Deutschland GmbH
Kreetslag 10, 21129 Hamburg, Germany
Chuanjun.Liu@airbus.com

SUMMARY

Fibre-metal laminates (FML) have been successfully used in Airbus A380 aircraft. As one of the essential airworthiness requirements, the material/structure defects have to be handled properly to make sure that they do not have detrimental effects on the load carrying capacity of the airframes. In order to numerically catch the effects of defects, e.g. delamination, on the buckling behavior of the FML panels, a 3D FE models are constructed based on the fuselage stiffened panels, artificial delaminations are introduced into the model, and their influence on the buckling onset and ultimate failure is then investigated numerically. As a specific failure mode, inter-rivet delamination buckling is also investigated.

Keywords: *Fiber-metal laminates, effects of defects, delamination, buckling, 3D FEM*

INTRODUCTION

Fibre-metal laminates (FML), which consist of alternate layers of metal alloys and fibre reinforced polymers, have been successfully used in Airbus A380 aircraft, as shown in Figure 1. A specific type of FML is Glare, which are built up of aluminium alloy sheets with thickness between 0.2 and 0.5 mm and oriented unidirectional glass fibre prepreg layers.

Figure 1 Material application in A380

Due to their excellent fatigue/damage resistance, FML are a very promising type of structural materials for modern aircraft. Large amount of theoretical research and

experimental investigation have been performed on the fatigue resistance behavior of FML [1-3]. As a result of the crack bridging effects, the damage/crack growth rate is much lower in FML than in monolithic aluminium, especially in the case of penetration cracks. This brings huge operational benefits for inspection and maintenance. Furthermore, fiber-metal laminates show a generic nature which combining the advantageous features of monolithic Al alloy and of composites. Accordingly, they provide the superior damage tolerance against static loads and fatigue. Additionally, the density of FML is lower than their monolithic alloys, which brings the benefits of weight saving.

Local delamination buckling in FML

A few types of local failure may occur in FML and their structures, as shown in Figure . Figure 2 (a) shows the delamination buckling of a delaminated surface Al sheet. This type of local delamination buckling can occur under all of the load cases. Figure 2 (b) shows a local fiber layer buckles and fails at a defect location, where a void opens up to one side, and the other side is delaminated. Figure 2 (c) shows forced local fiber crippling: a fiber layer fails at a location of extremely high local deformation. Due to the occurrence of this kind of local failure, more local damage can occur under cyclic load.

Figure 2 Two types of local buckling: (a). Al delamination buckling, (b) local fibre buckling at a defect site, and (c) forced local fibre crippling.

This paper presents parts of the results from a research programme, the immediate goal of this investigation is, based on the numerical simulations and tests on predefined defect scenarios up to the ultimate load, to ensure that those defects which may occur in the stiffened panels do not cause unacceptable reduction in the load carrying capacity. In the numerical calculations, those parameters defining buckling onset, limit load (and ultimate load), local plasticity, and out-of-plane deformation are compared.

MATERIALS and MODELS

Model Idealization

The main idea behind the idealization is that the model should be constructed in such a way that the local failure events, like local buckling and plastic deformation, etc., can be easily identify and characterized. For this purpose, a skin panel with 2 stringers is used to study the compression load case, while the picture frame is used to represent the pure shear reactions of the stiffened panel. Furthermore, the airframe structures have to be modeled on its meso-scale (sublaminates or layer scale) at the location where a defect exists. Additionally, multiple contact bodies have to be defined properly to represent the laminates and sublaminates, as well as the fasteners, and to reproduce their deformation.

Buckling onset – linear

The buckling onset stress is estimated both linearly and nonlinearly. For a linear estimation of the buckling onset stresses, the first few eigenvalues are calculated. Then the buckling onset stress is estimated at incremental i :

$$\sigma_{bo}^{linear} = \sigma_{i-1} + \lambda(\delta\sigma) \quad (1)$$

where λ is the lowest of the calculated eigenvalues, $\delta\sigma$ is the applied load at incremental i , and σ_{i-1} is the total stress at incremental $i-1$. If the eigenvalue is extracted at the very first incremental, then $\sigma_{i-1} = 0$. Thus, the buckling onset stress is simply estimated:

$$\sigma_{bo}^{linear} = \lambda(\delta\sigma) \quad (2)$$

Buckling onset – non-linear

The buckling onset is also estimated from nonlinear calculations, where the well-known bifurcation curves, as shown in Figure 3 (where the stress values are normalized, the same below when not specified), are used to determine the load level at which the panel buckles. The buckling onset stress is then calculated.

Figure 3 Buckling onset estimation

Estimation of Ultimate Load and Limit Load

A method used to determine the ultimate failure is shown in Figure 4, together with the deformed panel (the deformation is 5 times enlarged). In this calculation, the failure point can be determined easily: the deformation curve as a function of the applied load becomes vertical at the failure point, and the calculation does not convergent even with a tiny increase in the applied load.

Figure 4 Determination of final failure and the deformed panel at failure.

When failure is reached, the average stress in the skin is calculated as the indicator of the ultimate load. The limit load is then derived from the ultimate load calculated:

$$\sigma_{LL} = \frac{\sigma_{UL}}{1.5} \quad (3)$$

MODEL VERIFICATION

Comparison with analytical solution

For a brief verification of the model, a simple analytical solution was used to evaluate the buckling onset stress of an aluminum reference panel with a correction in boundary conditions [4]:

$$\sigma_{bo} = K_C k_b E \left(\frac{t}{b} \right)^2 \quad (4)$$

where k_b is the boundary correction factor, which is about 0.9889 for a Al panel ($t=1.95$ mm in thickness) with a stringer pitch 190 mm, with two clamped ends and two hinged boundaries. Therefore, $K_C = 6.63$. The analytically estimated buckling onset stress is about 51.0 MPa. The present nonlinear calculations give 51.7 MPa, the average stress in

the skin. The maximum difference is about 1.5 %. The present linear estimation gives the buckling onset stress 55.2 MPa.

Comparison with analytical solution – Orthotropic plate with 4-clamped edges

The local buckling onset stress, a square of stacked orthotropic prepreg layers, was calculated by using the picture frame shear model with 4-clamped edges. As it was done for the surface AI delamination, the bifurcation curves were plotted to catch the buckling onset, as indicated by the points. The calculated buckling onset stresses from 1-, 2-, and 3-layer models, with clamped edges, are also shown in Figure 5. An analytical solution from reference [5] is used to check the converted curves for the symmetric lay-ups, the 1-layer case and the 3-layer case, as the lines shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5 Buckling onset stresses calculated from picture frame models for 3 prepreg lay-ups.

RESULTS and DISCUSSIONS

Buckling onset and failure calculation

Buckling onset - Linear and nonlinear calculations

The buckling onset stress is often estimated by linear calculations for traditional AI panels. As it can be simply concluded from table 1, this conclusion does hold for stiffened FML far-field panels. However, the linear calculation results deviates the nonlinear ones much more significant for panels with transverse splice.

Table 1 Overview of results for panels without defects

	FML A (1.95mm far field)			FML B (3mm far field)		
	Far field panel	Spliced panel	Transverse splice	Far field panel	Spliced panel	Transverse splice
BO_N	1	1.03	0.83	1	1.0	0.93
BO_L	1.01	1.08	1.08	1.04	1.08	1.13
UL	4.1	4.03	4.1	2.3	2.3	206.5
postbuckling ratio	4.1	3.9	4.9	2.3	2.3	2.31

Notes: BO_N: buckling onset calculated nonlinearly; BO_L: buckling onset calculated linearly; UL: relative ultimate load compared to buckling onset. All are relative values compared to buckling onset, nonlinear value for far field panel.

Further investigation indicates that it is impossible to use linear FE calculation for the estimation of delamination buckling. Figure 6 shows a few simulated pictures of the local buckling modes for a circular delamination, 25 mm in diameter. The left column shows the first three eigenvalues. The deformations captured in the nonlinear calculations are presented in the right column. It can be seen that the real local buckling modes captured in the nonlinear calculation are completely different from the linear estimation. Furthermore, it is not possible to estimate the local buckling onset stress correctly from the linear calculation.

Figure 6 Left/ Right: eigenvalue / deformation captured in linear calculation / nonlinear calculations, both for a delamination 25 mm in diameter.

Estimation of the ultimate load (UL)

The typical method used to determine the ultimate failure is shown in Figure . In a nonlinear calculation, the failure point can be determined easily: the deformation curve as a function of the applied load becomes vertical at the failure point, and the calculation does not converge even with a tiny increase in the applied load.

It can be seen from table 1 that the load carrying capacities of the panels without defects are more or less the same, regardless the fact that panel B is 1.5 times thicker than panel A. Further study indicates that the final failure is driven by the plastic deformation of the stringers in stead of the panels. All of the panels have the same stringer profile with a code number 149.

Post buckling ratio

The thinner FML panels show a much larger post buckling capability than the thicker FML panels. It seems that the post buckling capability does not change very much with the detail structures of the panels, like splice, etc. However, it will be reduced dramatically when the skin thickness increases. Therefore, when a higher post buckling capability is required, then a thinner skin thickness should be taken into account, bear in mind that the final failure is dominated by the stringer plastic deformation.

Effects of artificial defects

A few defect scenarios were defined to study the effects of defects, as shown in table 2. Again, both linear and nonlinear calculations are performed to exam the effects.

However, the transverse splice case is not taken into account due to its obvious nonlinear and relatively large deformation before buckling onset.

Compared the values in table 1 and 2, one can simply obtain the following conclusions: the defined artificial defect scenarios have no numerically detectable effects on the buckling onset stress and on the failure load. Again, giving the fact that failure is dominated by the plastic deformation of the stringers, the defined defects should have no influence on the final failure, e.g. the ultimate load carrying capacity. Accordingly, the post buckling ratio is not affected by the defects.

Table 2 Overview of results for panels with defined defect scenarios

	FML A (1.95mm far field)				FML B (3mm far field)			
	Far field panel		Spliced panel		Far field panel		Spliced panel	
	C4_end	C4_mid	C1R3	C2R2	C4_end	C4_mid	C1R3	C2R2
BO_N	1	0.98	1.0	1.0	1	1.03	1.03	1
BO_L	0.97	0.99	1.09	1.08	1.09	1.04	1.05	1.1
UL				4.02	2.3			2.35
Post buckling ratio				4.0	2.3			2.3

Notes: BO_N and BO_L: buckling onset calculated nonlinearly and linearly, respectively. UL: estimated ultimate strength. All are relative values compared to buckling onset, nonlinear value for far field panel. Defect code: C4_end and C4_mid: 4 circular delaminations at the end and at the middle of the panel, respectively; C1R3: 1 circular delamination plus 3 rectangular delaminations, etc.

However, compared to the nonlinear calculation, the linear calculation tends to predict higher buckling onset for the cases with defects, which can be as high as 10%. The root cause behind is not very clear. Furthermore, when the size of the defect, for example a delamination, becomes larger, linear calculation will also become invalid for the buckling onset prediction, as indicated in Figure .

Inter-rivet delamination buckling (IRDB)

The following section presents part of the results dealing with inter-rivet delamination buckling for FML A. Please be informed, the strains are given in nominal values.

Cases without delamination

Figure shows the out-of-plane deformation for the four rivet pitches: $p = 25, 30, 35,$ and 40 mm. The buckling onset stresses calculated are 237 MPa, 207 MPa, 178 MPa, and 157 MPa for $p=25, 30, 35,$ and 40 mm for the FML, respectively. Accordingly, the buckling onset stresses of the Al structure (2 mm in thickness) are 308 MPa, 265MPa, 239 MPa and 208 MPa , respectively. If the thickness influence (2 mm to 1.95 mm, which is about 5%) can be ignored, then a simple comparison between the FML skin and the Al skin can be done for the same rivet-pitch. This obtains 77%, 78%, 74.5%, and 75.5% for the four cases. As it is known, the moduli ratio in the loading direction of the FML skin and Al skin is about 75%. Therefore, for the same thickness, the IRB onset stress reduces in a rate proportional to the modulus reduction of the skin. This

agreement may be an extra evidence, in case of lacking any direct experimental evidence, to show the correctness of the model.

Figure 7 FML4B-3/2-0.4mm skin response to IRB: no delamination case

Figure 8 Determination of the maximum reduction in IRB stress

Worst case: delamination length = rivet pitch

It is assumed that the maximum reduction is reached when the delamination length is the same as the rivet pitch. Accordingly, the buckling onset stresses are 181 MPa, 151 MPa, 122 MPa, and 102 MPa, as shown in Figure . Comparing to the critical IRDB stresses obtained above, the maximum reduction of IRDB onset can be estimated: $1-0.76=0.24$, $1-0.73=0.27$, $1-0.69=0.31$, and $1-0.65=0.35$ for rivet pitch 25mm, 30mm, 35mm, and 40 mm, respectively, for the given prestress level.

Besides the maximum reduction, another phenomenon observed is that the delaminated laminate (the two sublaminates) buckles as one body at buckling onset. After this global buckling, the two sublaminates start to separate due to the difference in their deformation. Thus, a gap forms between the two sublaminates. See the separation from the curves below. This means that the load carrying capacity of the local structure is reduced due to the delamination.

Delamination length influence: surface Al delamination

In order to get the critical IRDB stresses as a function of the delamination length, two cases are calculated: $p=40$ mm and $p=35$ mm. For the first case, 5 delamination lengths are calculated. The results are presented in Figure 9 and 10. For the second case, the critical IRDB stresses for 4 delamination lengths are estimated. The delamination length decreases about 10 mm each. From these curves presented in Figure 9 and Figure 10, one can obtain some conclusions:

- (1). When the delamination length is smaller than 10 mm, the delamination effect will be negligible on IRB.
- (2). When the delamination length is in between 10 mm to 20 mm, the separation of the two sublaminates is not obvious.

Figure 9 Delamination length effects on IRDB: $p=35$ mm

Figure 10 Delamination length effects on IRDB: $p=35$ mm

Discussions

Prestress effects on IRDB

The prestress effects on the IRDB are investigated for a case of $p=6D$, where D is the rivet diameter. The delamination length is the same with the rivet pitch. Then, different prestresses are applied and the correspondent IRDB responses are calculated. The result are presented in Figure 11 together with the case without delamination. A higher prestress has two effects:

- (1). make the surface Al buckle later,
- (2). make the sublaminates buckles as one body.

However, the effects of this prestress become less significant when it is significantly high. This is because the plastic deformation of the rivet will first diminish the effects. As a result, the critical IRDB stresses will tend to a constant value with the increased prestress level.

Figure 11 Effects of prestress on inter-rivet delamination buckling

Conclusions

Based on this investigation, it can be concluded:

1. For the prediction of the buckling onset of a stiffened FML panel, linear FE gives acceptable prediction for far field panels. However, a linear FE calculation is not able to catch local delamination buckling onset, including the case with splice for panel buckling. Therefore, nonlinear FE calculation must be performed to estimate the safety margin.
2. For the defined defect scenarios, it seems that the ultimate strength of the panel is determined by the stringers, the skin thickness (FML type) has little influence on this strength. In fact, it was observed that the final failure of the reinforced panel is a result of the plastic deformation of the stringers.
3. When the delamination is smaller than 15 mm to 20 mm, its effects on the IRDB stress are not very obvious. When delamination is small than 10 mm, no effect has been observed. The prestress applied in the rivet installation is also an important parameter to control.

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